

1 **Electrospinning of softwood kraft lignin with cellulose acetate:**
2 **dye adsorption, carbonization and carbon dioxide capture**

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7

8 **Abstract**

9 The development of bio-based materials capable of addressing multiple environmental
10 challenges is critical for advancing sustainable materials design. Herein, we report electrospun
11 nanofibers from unfractionated, chemically unmodified softwood kraft lignin and cellulose
12 acetate, where cellulose acetate acts as a carrier polymer, enabling the formation of uniform
13 precursor fibers with lignin contents of up to 80%. The resulting nanofibers enable sequential
14 dye adsorption from water (methylene blue removal capacity of 19 mg/g) and carbon dioxide
15 (CO₂) capture (2.2 mmol/g) after carbonization. When evaluated solely for CO₂ capture, the
16 pristine carbonized materials show sorption capacities of 3.1–3.9 mmol/g, which increase as
17 lignin content in the precursor fibers decreases, underscoring the importance of tuning carbon
18 yield and capture performance. The sequential utilization of single precursor material
19 demonstrates a stepwise transformation that aligns with resource efficiency and sustainable
20 material design. Overall, this study demonstrates a viable route for the direct valorization of
21 industrial lignin into functional materials for both water purification and carbon capture
22 applications.

23

24 *Keywords: Softwood kraft lignin, Electrospinning, Carbonization, Dye adsorption, CO₂*
25 *sorption*

26 **Introduction**

27 The rapid expansion of industrial activities has intensified two interconnected challenges, water
28 contamination and rising atmospheric carbon dioxide (CO₂) levels, with the latter being the
29 primary driver of climate change.¹ Mitigating CO₂ emissions while enabling efficient
30 remediation of industrial effluents is thus central to achieving climate neutrality and circular
31 economy goals. Carbon capture technologies² and adsorption-based separation processes have
32 gained renewed attention, driven by the need for scalable, energy-efficient, and sustainable
33 material solutions. Conventional sorbent materials and treatment methods, while being
34 effective, often suffer from limitations such as regeneration efficiency and reliance on non-
35 renewable resources.³ Recent studies on adsorbent materials have focused on tailoring high
36 surface area and chemical structures to enhance pollutant uptake,⁴ with increased emphasis on
37 renewable feedstocks driving interest in bio-derived alternatives.

38 Adsorption-based separation has become a central strategy for addressing water
39 pollution and carbon dioxide capture. A wide range of materials have been explored for gas
40 and dye adsorption, including protein nanofibrils,⁵ metal–organic frameworks (MOFs),^{6–8}
41 porous organic polymers,^{9–11} ionic liquids,¹² and carbon-based materials,¹³ many of which
42 show high adsorption capacities but rely on complex, energy-intensive synthesis and non-
43 renewable precursors. For carbon capture, porous carbons remain among the most widely used
44 sorbents because of their tunable porosity,¹⁴ chemical resistance,¹⁵ and thermal stability.¹⁶
45 Simultaneously, increasing attention has turned to biomass-derived carbons, particularly lignin,
46 owing to its high aromatic carbon content and suitability for conversion into porous
47 structures.^{17,18} Over the last decade, lignin has been explored in various forms including

48 powders,^{19,20} particles,²¹ fibers,²² and foams,²³ which can potentially be used for the fabrication
49 of carbon materials.

50 One of the emerging routes for lignin valorization is electrospinning.²⁴ Producing lignin
51 fibers by electrospinning is challenging without chemical modification or solvent fractionation,
52 due to the presence of low-molecular-weight fractions and the inherent heterogeneity of
53 lignin.^{25,26} Though electrospinning of the mere technical lignin generally results in electro-
54 spraying of lignin particles,²⁷ there have been multiple approaches to improve the spinnability
55 by adding a binder polymer such as poly(ethylene oxide) (PEO),^{28,29} poly(acrylonitrile)
56 (PAN),^{30,31} poly(lactic acid) (PLA),³² poly(vinyl alcohol) (PVA),³³ cellulose acetate (CA),
57 ^{27,34,35} or by solvent fractionation of lignin.^{36,37} Previous studies on electrospinning of lignin-
58 cellulose acetate systems have primarily focused on hardwood kraft lignins.³⁴ Moreover,
59 lignin-based electrospun fibers have largely focused on single-function applications such as
60 water purification or carbonization for gas sorption or energy storage.

61 In the present work, we report the electrospinning of softwood kraft lignin (SKL) in the
62 presence of cellulose acetate (CA), achieving precursor fiber mats with up to 80 wt.% lignin.
63 Using CA as the sole binder polymer for electrospinning enabled a fully bio-based fiber system
64 while reducing the processing complexity associated with lignin fractionation or modification.
65 The electrospun fibers were first evaluated for methylene blue adsorption from water and were
66 subsequently carbonized for CO₂ capture. In comparison, carbonization of pristine fibers
67 without prior dye adsorption resulted in higher CO₂ uptake than fibers carbonized after dye
68 loading. These observations indicate that adsorbed dye interferes with pore development during
69 carbonization. Overall, the results highlight the dual role of lignin in carbon fiber production:
70 lignin is essential for achieving high carbon yields and structural integrity during thermal
71 stabilization, while the surface area and micropore volume of the resulting carbon can be
72 systematically tuned by adjusting the lignin content in the precursor fiber mats.

73

74 **Results and Discussion**

75 **Optimisation of lignin nanofiber electrospinning**

76 Electrospinning apparatus with a rotating drum collector, as shown in **Fig. 1a**, was employed
77 for an efficient, long duration, and continuous spinning of softwood kraft lignin (SKL)–
78 cellulose acetate (CA) solutions with different formulations. Electrospinning solutions were
79 first obtained by dissolving SKL and CA in 0:100, 50:50, 60:40, 70:30 and 80:20 wt.%,
80 respectively, in a 1:2.4 v/v ratio of DMF/acetone solvent mixture, as shown in **Fig. 1b**. After
81 several trial-and-error experiments, the values for the electrospinning parameters, such as flow
82 rate, electrospinning voltage, distance between the nozzle and the collector as well as speed of
83 the rotating drum collector, were optimized. **Fig. 1c–g** show the digital images of the nanofiber
84 mats formed after 5–6 hours of electrospinning at a flow rate of 0.03 mL/min, 20 kV voltage,
85 20 cm distance between the collector and the spinneret, and 130 rpm rotating drum speed.
86 Similarly, an SKL–CA solution with a 100:0 wt.% composition primarily resulted in
87 electrospayed lignin particles rather than fibers.

88

89

90 **Figure 1. Electrospinning of lignin–cellulose acetate fibers.** (a) Illustration of
 91 electrospinning setup with a rotating drum collector and the nanofibers formed. (b)
 92 Formulations of electrospinning solution used to spin the nanofibers (SKL–CA) shown in the
 93 digital images (c) 0:100, (d) 50:50, (e) 60:40, (f) 70:30 and (g) 80:20 wt.% respectively
 94 (electrospun fiber sheets were cut into circular pieces for representation only).

95

96 Previous studies on lignin electrospinning have largely relied on blending lignin with a
 97 polymer to achieve sufficient spinnability. The lignin content in these prior studies has been up
 98 to 70% in the case of hardwood kraft lignin from poplar and eucalyptus. Alternatively,
 99 electrospinning of fractionated lignin without additives has been reported, yet these approaches
 100 rely on solvent-intensive fractionation of lignin.^{36,37} Electrospinning of lignin without binder
 101 polymers has been demonstrated for softwood organosolv lignin; however, to suppress the bead

102 formation and to improve the fiber uniformity, addition of iron (III) chloride was required.³⁸ In
103 some systems, lignin's tendency to electro spray has been deliberately utilized to produce fiber
104 bead structures using hardwood kraft lignin from eucalyptus/CA.²⁷ Since pure lignin lacks
105 sufficient chain entanglement and viscoelasticity for fiber spinning, it is commonly blended
106 with polymers such as PAN,^{30,31,39} PEO,^{28,29} PLA,³² and CA,³⁴ to improve the
107 electrospinnability. These compositional and rheological factors influence the morphology of
108 the resulting electrospun fibers.

109 The effect of SKL–CA composition on fiber formation and morphology during
110 electrospinning was systematically examined using scanning electron microscopy. **Fig. 2a–e**
111 displays the SEM images of the morphology of the electrospun/electrosprayed SKL–CA
112 solutions with composition 0:100, 50:50, 60:40, 70:30, 80:20 and 100:0 wt.% respectively.
113 SEM analysis shows uniform and continuous fibers for SKL contents between 0 and 80 wt.%,
114 when electrospun with CA as a binder polymer, demonstrating stable fiber formation across a
115 wide lignin composition range, as evident from **Fig. 2a–e**. From the attempt to use SKL in the
116 absence of CA, it is evident that electrospinning requires polymeric substances that can
117 undergo molecular entanglements, since SKL alone only produced electro sprayed particles
118 (**Fig. 2f**). Similar observations have been previously published with hardwood kraft lignin.³⁴
119 In addition to its rheological properties that allow electrospinning, CA improves the
120 processability and spinnability of the electrospinning solutions through molecular interactions
121 such as H–bonding with SKL.⁴⁰ Moreover, binders that participate in H–bonding with lignin
122 typically improve miscibility and spinnability of lignin solutions which also results in the
123 formation of uniform continuous fibers.^{41,42}

124 The diameter of electrospun nanofibers is a crucial parameter as it governs the surface
125 area as well as the porosity of the resulting nanofiber mat and it is influenced by several factors
126 such as the distance between spinneret and the collector plate, applied voltage, concentration

127 of the spinning solution, flow rate, conductivity of the spinning solution etc.⁴³ Gaussian
128 distributions of the fiber/particle diameter are given in **Fig. 2g–l**. The mean diameter of the
129 fibers formed by CA alone was 304 nm and for the SKL–CA compositions of 50:50, 60:40,
130 70:30 and 80:20 wt.%, the mean fiber diameters were 183 nm, 248 nm, 275 nm and 301 nm,
131 respectively. For SKL electro spraying, the mean particle diameter was found to be 188 nm,
132 with a homogenous particle size distribution, meaning electro spraying can be efficiently
133 employed for the formation of lignin nanoparticles. Quantitative analysis of the fiber diameters
134 revealed that all lignin-containing fibers fall within the sub-micrometer range, with only
135 moderate variations observed as the SKL content increases. The similarity in fiber diameters
136 across different SKL content suggests that the solution properties remained within a stable
137 electrospinning regime, which enabled effective electrospinning jet stretching, despite the
138 higher loading of SKL. The fiber diameter depends on electrospinning parameters as well as
139 the type of the lignin and the concentration of the spinning solution.^{44,45} For example, hardwood
140 kraft lignin from eucalyptus/CA and hardwood kraft lignin from poplar/CA systems exhibited
141 comparable nanofiber diameters and porosity due to their similar solution characteristics,
142 whereas hardwood kraft lignin from olive tree pruning (OTP)/CA produced significantly
143 thinner fibers due to the higher shear viscosity and electrical conductivity of the spinning
144 solutions.³⁴

145

146

147 **Figure 2. Scanning electron microscopic images and dimensional analysis of electrospun**

148 **SKL-CA materials.** Electrospinning of SKL-CA solutions with following composition in

149 wt.% (a) 0:100, (b) 50:50, (c) 60:40, (d) 70:30, (e) 80:20, and (f) 100:0. Gaussian distribution

150 of fiber/particle diameters based on scanning electron microscopic images of electrospun

151 materials with the following compositions in wt.% (g) 0:100, (h) 50:50, (i) 60:40, (j) 70:30, (k)

152 80:20 and (l) 100:0.

153

154

155 The thermal degradation of the electrospun fibers was investigated by TGA to evaluate
156 their thermostabilization behavior. Samples were heated in air from room temperature to 340
157 °C at a heating rate of 2 °C min⁻¹, followed by an isothermal hold at 340 °C for 60 min. Pristine
158 CA exhibited a single-step degradation with an onset temperature of approximately 260 °C,
159 resulting in a total weight loss of 82.8% (**Fig. S1**). In contrast, SKL displayed a two-step
160 degradation profile. The first weight-loss event occurred around 70 °C and corresponded to
161 moisture loss, accounting for approximately 30% of mass loss. The second step started
162 gradually at around 200 °C, leading to an additional weight loss of approximately 17% by 340
163 °C. During the subsequent isothermal hold, a further 13% mass loss was observed, resulting in
164 a total weight loss of approximately 60% for SKL. Similarly, the electrospun fibers exhibited
165 a multi-step degradation behavior. An initial weight loss of 1–5% was observed at around 60
166 °C, which is attributed to the removal of adsorbed moisture. This was followed by a gradual
167 weight loss starting at approximately 150 °C, corresponding to the slow evaporation of residual
168 solvent, contributing an additional ~7% mass loss. A more pronounced decrease in weight was
169 then observed between 250 °C and 340 °C, associated with the onset of thermal degradation.
170 Notably, the overall weight loss decreased slightly with increasing SKL content in the fibers.
171 Electrospun fibers composed solely of CA showed thermal degradation behavior like that of
172 pristine CA (**Fig. 3a**), with a total weight loss of approximately 80%. In contrast, fibers
173 containing SKL exhibited significantly lower total weight loss (~60%), indicating enhanced
174 thermal stability upon incorporation of lignin (**Fig. S1**).

175 ATR-FTIR spectroscopy was used to identify and compare the characteristic functional
176 groups of SKL, CA and the electrospun fibers. For SKL, a wide band around 3000–3400 cm⁻¹
177 was assigned to phenolic and aliphatic —OH stretching vibrations (**Fig. 3b**). A band near 2937
178 cm⁻¹ is attributed to C—H stretching in the methyl and methylene groups of the side chains and
179 aromatic methoxy groups.^{46,47} The band around 1034 cm⁻¹ is attributed to C—O deformation

180 mainly in primary alcohol, aliphatic ethers, as well as C—H in aromatic rings. The band around
181 1215 cm^{-1} is assigned to C—C, C—O and C=O stretch mainly from condensed guaiacyl units.
182 The narrow band at 1514 cm^{-1} is assigned to aromatic ring vibrations.⁴⁸ As shown in **Fig. 3b**,
183 the ATR-FTIR spectra of CA has two distinct bands at around 1735 cm^{-1} and 1215 cm^{-1}
184 corresponding to stretching vibration modes of C=O of the acetyl group and C—O stretching
185 vibrations, respectively.⁴⁹ The peak at 1026 cm^{-1} is assigned to the C—O—C asymmetric
186 stretching of the ether group in the pyranose ring. The less intense band at 900 cm^{-1} is due to
187 the C—H out of plane deformation.⁵⁰ ATR-FTIR spectra of electrospun SKL–CA fibers are
188 shown in **Fig. 3c**. Compared to the individual components, similar but less intense bands were
189 observed for the electrospun SKL–CA fiber mats. A decrease in intensity and broadening of
190 the —OH stretching band is observed at around 3500 cm^{-1} , suggesting possible H–bonding
191 between SKL and CA. Because of the interactions between —OH group of SKL and C=O
192 groups of CA, the O–H bond weakens as the electron density of the —OH group is shared and
193 which results in the decrease of vibrational frequency.⁵¹ The weak band at $\sim 3000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is related
194 to the C—H stretching in methyl and methoxy groups of SKL and CA.⁵² The intense band
195 around 1750 cm^{-1} is attributed to the C=O stretching vibrations of acetyl groups from CA.
196 Integration of the spectra within $1700\text{--}1790\text{ cm}^{-1}$ showed a linear correlation to the CA content
197 in SKL–CA electrospun fibers (**Fig. 3d**). The band around 1500 cm^{-1} corresponds to the
198 aromatic skeletal vibrations from guaiacyl units of SKL, and 1232 cm^{-1} corresponds to the C—
199 C, C—O, and C=O stretch mainly from condensed guaiacyl units. The band at 1040 cm^{-1} is
200 attributed to the C—O deformation mainly from primary alcohol, aliphatic ethers, and C—H
201 in aromatic rings, and the peak around 890 cm^{-1} corresponds to C—H deformation out of the
202 plane of the hydrogens from p-hydroxyphenyl units.⁴⁸

203
 204 **Figure 3: Thermal and spectroscopic properties of SKL-CA nanofiber mats with**
 205 **different compositions.** (a) TGA thermogram in air. ATR-FTIR spectra of (b) CA and SKL,
 206 (c) electrospun products from SKL-CA at different composition. (d) Integrated band area at
 207 1700–1790 cm⁻¹ from (c) as a function of the theoretical cellulose acetate content.

208

209 Adsorption of methylene blue by electrospun nanofibers

210 The electrospun SKL-CA nanofiber mats with the highest lignin content (80 wt.%) were used
 211 as an adsorbent material for methylene blue, which is a cationic dye. Prior to the adsorption
 212 experiment, the water contact angle of the nanofiber mat was assessed. Although SKL and CA
 213 contain polar groups, such as hydroxyl functional groups, the high surface roughness of the
 214 nanofiber mats resulted in a static water contact angle of 155 ° which reduced to 55 ° in 60

215 seconds (**Fig. 4a**). Similar behavior has been reported for an electrospun lignin/ZnO
216 nanofibrous membrane.⁵³ To facilitate the surface wetting for dye adsorption, electrospun
217 nanofibers taken in the vial containing dye solutions were hand-shaken a few times before
218 placing them in the shaking incubator. **Fig. 4b** shows the digital images of dye solutions before
219 and after contact with electrospun nanofibers for 24 h. Adsorption kinetics were performed
220 using an initial dye concentration of 75 mg/L for 24 h. The kinetics revealed a rapid dye uptake
221 (~ 32 %) within the first 30 minutes, followed by a slower diffusion-limited adsorption stage
222 that continues over approximately 24 h, resulting in a comparable additional dye removal, as
223 shown in **Fig. 4c**. The adsorption kinetics curve suggests that readily accessible adsorption sites
224 are occupied first, in the first 30 minutes, while subsequent adsorption is governed by slower
225 mass transport processes. The absence of a sharp increase in dye removal over the period of
226 the kinetics experiment indicates that strong electrostatic interactions are not dominant in this
227 system, and the adsorption is mainly physically driven. This physical interaction can be weak
228 interactions such as van der Waals forces or π - π interactions between aromatic moieties of
229 SKL and methylene blue dye molecules. This is further corroborated by the lower values for
230 adsorption capacities that we found compared to the literature. For instance, when modified
231 Indulin AT samples were used for methylene blue dye removal, with a maximum adsorption
232 capacity of up to 55 mg/g, 61 % of the interaction between the dye molecule and lignin was
233 found to be H-bonding and 38 % through electrostatic interactions.⁵⁴ However, when lignin
234 extracted from sugarcane bagasse was employed for methylene blue removal, the maximum
235 adsorption capacity was determined to be 14 mg/g, because of the weak binding between the
236 adsorbent and the adsorbate.⁵⁵

237 Lower dye concentrations of 7, 16, and 38 mg/L showed significant dye removal
238 efficiency of 95.7, 99.6, and 94.5 % respectively with equilibrium adsorption capacities of 2.2,
239 5.2, and 12.0 mg/g respectively. For higher concentrations such as 75, 109, and 142 mg/L, the

240 dye removal efficiency was reduced to 66, 45, and 40% respectively, with equilibrium
241 adsorption capacities of 16.6, 16.2, and 18.8 mg/g, respectively (**Fig. 4d**). A plateauing trend
242 in adsorption capacity was observed for initial dye concentration ≥ 75 mg/L, suggesting the
243 saturation of accessible adsorption sites. Equilibrium adsorption data were analyzed using
244 Langmuir, Freundlich, and Langmuir–Freundlich adsorption isotherm models to gain insight
245 into the adsorption mechanism and the corresponding fitting results are summarized in **Table**
246 **S1**. The Langmuir model assumes a monolayer adsorption⁵⁶ and suggests that adsorption
247 initially occurs at energetically favorable sites as seen from **Fig. 4d**. In contrast, the Freundlich
248 model describes adsorption on a heterogenous surface with varying adsorption energies.⁵⁵ This
249 surface heterogeneity is expected for the electrospun fiber mats as well as for SKL because of
250 the diverse functional groups in lignin. The combined Langmuir and Freundlich model that
251 fits the experimental data suggests that methylene blue adsorption on electrospun fiber mats
252 involves monolayer adsorption at lower equilibrium concentrations followed by the slow
253 occupation of heterogenous sites at higher equilibrium concentrations.

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 258 **Figure 4. Dye adsorption application.** (a) Water contact angle measurements of 80:20
 259 electrospun fiber mat recorded as a function of time, (b) Digital images showing methylene
 260 blue dye solutions of different initial concentrations before and after 24 h of adsorption by
 261 80:20 electrospun fibers, (c) Adsorption kinetics of methylene blue dye ($C_0 = 75$ mg/L) on
 262 80:20 electrospun fibers showing % dye removal as a function of contact time varying from 0–
 263 24 h and (d) Equilibrium adsorption isotherms showing equilibrium adsorption capacity (Q_e ,
 264 mg/g) as a function of equilibrium dye concentration (C_e , mg/L) with Langmuir, Freundlich
 265 and Langmuir–Freundlich model fits for dye adsorption after 24 h using initial methylene blue
 266 dye concentrations of 7–142 mg/L using 80:20 electrospun fiber mat.

267

268 Influence of thermostabilization on fiber fusion

269 The goal of the thermostabilization method was to limit melting of lignin in SKL–CA
 270 electrospun nanofibers during carbonization, with the intention of enhancing the total pore
 271 volume. The procedure followed for thermostabilization and carbonization of the SKL–CA
 272 electrospun nanofibers with different lignin contents is presented in **Fig.5**.

273

274 **Figure 5. Illustration of procedure used for thermostabilization and carbonization of**
 275 **electrospun SKL-CA nanofibers.**

276

277 Oxidative stabilization of nanofibers induces chemical changes such as dehydration,
 278 oxidation, and cross-linking,⁵⁷ which are essential for preserving fiber morphology during the
 279 subsequent carbonization step. It is also expected that residual solvent traces will also leave the
 280 system during thermostabilization, which will eventually increase the porosity of the
 281 carbonized fibers. Stabilization temperature of 300 °C was selected based on the TGA results
 282 (**Fig. 3a**), where electrospun CA nanofibers begin to thermally degrade at ~300 °C and SKL-
 283 CA nanofibers begin to slowly degrade at ~280 °C. This temperature marks the optimum
 284 compromise temperature at which lignin undergoes effective oxidative crosslinking, improving
 285 thermal stability upon carbonization.^{58,59} The digital images of thermostabilized fibers as well
 286 as carbonized fibers corresponding to all the prepared compositions are showcased in the **Fig.**
 287 **S3**. In the present study, nanofiber mats with higher lignin content (SKL:CA 70:30 and 80:20)
 288 exhibited effective thermostabilization, maintaining the majority of the fiber shape after
 289 stabilization at 300 °C when the heating rate was 2°C/min (**Fig. S4** and **Fig. S5**). The
 290 thermostabilization yield (Y_{TS} , %) of these samples were 66% and 64% respectively with
 291 respect to the initial weight of the fiber mats. In contrast, nanofiber mats with higher CA
 292 content (SKL:CA 0:100, 50:50, and 60:40) exhibited insufficient thermostabilization,
 293 characterized by significant fiber fusion during oxidative treatment (**Fig. S6** and **Fig. S7**). This
 294 behavior is attributed to the thermoplastic nature of CA, which softens under stabilization

295 conditions.⁶⁰ Thermostabilization yield (Y_{TS} , %) of these materials was 58% and 60%,
296 respectively. For thermostabilized fibers from pure CA, Y_{TS} was found to be 33%, which is the
297 lowest yield among all the thermostabilized fibers with different compositions of SKL therein.
298 Importantly, the thermoplastic softening of CA during thermostabilization can be viewed as a
299 sacrificial process that facilitates internal phase rearrangement, which contributes to the
300 development of porosity upon subsequent carbonization, while lignin serves as the primary
301 structure-retaining component. Despite the loss of fibrous network, CA contributed
302 substantially to the surface area more than SKL did. Similar observations have been reported
303 in lignin–PLA electrospun systems, where the thermoplastic PLA component underwent phase
304 separation during stabilization and subsequently acted as a sacrificial polymer, enhancing the
305 porosity of carbon fibers formed.³²

306

307 **Carbonized electrospun SKL–CA nanofibers**

308 Carbonization of the thermostabilized fibers was carried out in an inert atmosphere, by heating
309 the sample up to 1000 °C with a heating rate of 5 °C/min with an isothermal hold for 60 min
310 at 1000 °C, followed by cooling at 10 °C/min to room temperature. The yield of carbonization
311 with respect to the initial electrospun fiber mat weight, Y_C (%) is given in **Table 1**, which
312 ranged from 0.8–36 %, generally increasing with increasing lignin content. The SEM images
313 of the carbonized fibers along with the Gaussian distribution of pore sizes are presented in **Fig.**
314 **6a–d**, and the size of the pores was analyzed from the corresponding SEM images using
315 ImageJ. All fibers exhibited a wide range of pore size distribution ranging from 0.01–0.1 μm .
316 Carbonized fibers with higher lignin content maintained the fiber shape compared to
317 carbonized fibers with lower lignin content or no lignin at all. Additional images of carbonized
318 fibers with SKL–CA composition 50:50, 60:40, 70:30, and 80:20 wt.% are shown in **Fig. S8**,

319 **Fig. S9, Fig. S10, and Fig. S11**, respectively. A SEM image of the carbonized pure cellulose
 320 acetate fiber is presented in **Fig. S7**, revealing the high porosity of the carbonized material.

321

322 **Table 1. Thermostabilization and carbonization data.** Thermostabilization yield (Y_{TS}),
 323 Carbonization yield (Y_C), Carbonization yield with respect to thermostabilization ($Y_{C/TS}$), BET
 324 surface area and atomic % of C, N and O from EDS of carbonized SKL–CA nanofiber mats
 325 with different compositions in wt.%.

SKL– CA ratio (wt.%)	Y_{TS} (%)	Y_C (%)	$Y_{C/TS}$ (%)	BET SA (m^2/g)	Micropore volume (cm^3/g)	C (at– %) ¹	N (at–%) ¹	O (at–%) ¹
0:100	33	0.8	2	–	–	–	–	–
50:50	58	9	15	773 ± 9	0.21	86.1 ± 0.1	0.78 ± 0.0	10.3 ± 0.0
60:40	60	17	29	536 ± 8	0.14	87.5 ± 0.9	0.5 ± 0.6	10.6 ± 0.8
70:30	66	36	55	63 ± 12	0.02	90.1 ± 0.3	4.3 ± 0.4	4.9 ± 0.2
80:20	64	35	55	41 ± 8	0.01	88.2 ± 0.2	4.9 ± 0.3	6.0 ± 0.1

326 ¹: Atomic percentage from EDS.

327

328 To shed light on the porous carbons their BET surface areas were determined by N₂
 329 adsorption. The measured BET surface area ranged from 41–773 m²/g and decreased with
 330 increasing lignin content, as it restricts the pore development observed from the SEM images
 331 and micropore volume analysis. Higher content of CA was found to be essential for the
 332 development of pores. Specifically, fibers containing 80, 70, 60, and 50 wt.% SKL exhibited
 333 BET surface areas of 41, 63, 536, and 773 m²/g, respectively (**Table 1**). The micropore volume
 334 of the porous carbons ranged from 0.01–0.21 cm³/g. The micropore volume increased with
 335 respect to the CA content in the precursor fibers, which acts as a sacrificial polymer leaving
 336 high porosity. The trend of decreasing micropore volume with higher lignin content was in
 337 accordance with the BET surface area measured. Based on EDS mapping of carbonized SKL–

338 CA electrospun fiber mats their carbon content ranged from 86% to 94% (**Table 1**). EDS maps
 339 of carbonized fibers solely made from CA are given in **Fig. S7**, which showed 86 atomic % of
 340 carbon along with 11 atomic % of oxygen, 3 atomic % of nitrogen, and traces of other elements.
 341 Similarly, EDS maps of carbonized fibers with SKL–CA composition 50:50 wt.%, 60:40 wt.%,
 342 70:30 wt.% and 80:20 wt.% are given in the supplementary figures **Fig. S8**, **Fig. S9**, **Fig. S10**
 343 and **Fig. S11**, respectively.

344

345

346 **Figure 6. Pore size analysis of carbonized SKL–CA electrospun fibers.** Pore size
 347 distributions with Gaussian fitting curves for carbonized SKL–CA nanofibers with
 348 composition in wt.% (a) 50:50, (b) 60:40, (c) 70:30 and (d) 80:20. Inset in each panel show the
 349 corresponding SEM images of the fibers and the scale bars in the SEM images denote 2 μm .

350

351 The structural evolution of SKL–CA fiber mats during thermostabilization and
352 carbonization was analyzed using XRD, Raman spectroscopy, ATR-FTIR, and solid-state ¹³C
353 MAS NMR. **Fig. S1** shows the X-Ray Diffractogram of pristine CA and SKL. The XRD pattern
354 of CA exhibits the usual peaks around $2\theta = 17^\circ$ and 21° ,⁶¹ which is typical for semi-crystalline
355 materials,⁶² and SKL exhibits a broad peak around $2\theta = 20^\circ$ indicating its amorphous nature.⁶³
356 XRD pattern of the thermostabilized fibers maintained the peaks at $2\theta = 17^\circ$ and 21° , meaning
357 the crystallinity of the fibers was not affected by the thermostabilization at 300 °C. In the XRD
358 pattern of the carbonized SKL–CA fibers (**Fig. 7a**) a new peak around $2\theta = 44^\circ$ was observed
359 compared to the thermostabilized fibers, which is attributed to the reflection of the (100) plane
360 of amorphous carbon.⁶⁴

361

362

363 **Figure 7. Structural characterization and Nitrogen/carbon dioxide adsorption on**
 364 **carbonized SKL-CA nanofibers.** (a) X-Ray diffractogram, (b) Raman spectra, (c) ATR-FTIR
 365 spectra, (d) N₂ adsorption, (e) CO₂ adsorption isotherm at 0°C of the carbonized SKL-CA
 366 nanofibers with different composition in wt.% and (f) CO₂ adsorption isotherm at 0°C of the
 367 carbonized methylene blue adsorbed SKL-CA nanofibers with composition 80:20 in wt.%.

368

369 Raman spectra of carbonized fibers are shown in **Fig. 7b**. The Raman spectra show two
 370 clear and distinct intensity regions, ~ 1330 cm⁻¹, namely the D band and ~ 1590 cm⁻¹, namely

371 the G band. The broad peak between 2600–3000 cm^{-1} is also observed, corresponding to the
372 2D band. The D peak corresponds to the sp^2 breathing modes of the aromatic rings, and the G
373 peak corresponds to the in-plane bond stretching of sp^2 -hybridised carbon atoms in both rings
374 and chains,^{65–67} where the 2D band arises from a second-order two-phonon process.⁶⁸
375 Deconvoluted fits for all the Raman spectra collected are presented in the **Fig. S12**. The
376 intensity ratio of the D band to the G band gives the semiquantitative information about the
377 graphitic content. For this work, I_D/I_G ratio for all the carbonized fiber mats prepared was close
378 to unity, more precisely 1.1, 1.02, 0.99, 1.02 and 0.99 respectively for carbonized fiber mats
379 with SKL–CA composition 0:100, 50:50, 60:40, 70:30 and 80:20 wt.% respectively, which has
380 previously been reported for lignin-derived carbon fibers in the literature.^{22,60}

381 ATR-FTIR spectra of carbonized SKL–CA fibers presented in **Fig. 7c** are found to have
382 a low signal-to-noise ratio. A strong band around 1060 cm^{-1} and another band around 1250 cm^{-1}
383 is attributed to the presence of C—O—C stretching. The band between 2900 cm^{-1} –2990 cm^{-1}
384 is attributed to C—H stretching. The wavenumber region 1400–1750 cm^{-1} contains bands
385 assigned to C—N stretching, C—C stretching, and C=O stretching,⁶⁹ and the region around
386 3500 cm^{-1} associated with N—H stretching, exhibits significant spectral noise.

387

388 **Gas adsorption performance (CO₂/N₂ adsorption isotherm)**

389 N₂ adsorption isotherms were measured at 77.34 K and CO₂ isotherms were measured at 273
390 K and 1.0 bar, which is presented in **Fig. 7d** and **Fig. 7e**, respectively. At 273 K and 101 kPa,
391 carbonized fibers from SKL–CA 50:50 wt.% exhibited CO₂ uptake of 3.9 mmol/g and N₂
392 uptake of 12.0 mmol/g. With higher lignin content in the precursor fibers, the CO₂ uptake
393 gradually decreased. Carbonized fibers with 60:40 wt.% exhibited CO₂ uptake of 3.5 mmol/g
394 and N₂ uptake of 8.0 mmol/g. Carbonized fibers with 70:30 wt.% had a CO₂ uptake of 3.3
395 mmol/g and N₂ uptake of 1.0 mmol/g, and 80:20 wt.% showed a CO₂ uptake of 3.1 mmol/g

396 and N₂ uptake of 0.5 mmol/g. N₂ uptake for all the carbonized fibers was in accordance with
397 the BET surface area measured as reported in **Table 1**, but the CO₂ uptake for all the carbonized
398 fibers ranged from 3.1–3.9 mmol/g with decreasing SKL content. Interestingly, carbonized
399 fibers with higher lignin content and low surface area showed equally good CO₂ uptake as the
400 carbonized fibers with lower lignin content and higher surface area. The observed correlation
401 between BET surface area and N₂ uptake was not similar for CO₂ uptake, as the CO₂ adsorption
402 process is governed not only by the surface area but also by the surface chemistry and
403 micropore volume. The carbon materials in the present study exhibited high CO₂ uptake values,
404 even though the carbonized fibers were not subjected to any further activation after
405 fabrication,^{21,70} or doping before/during^{19,71,72} the carbonization process. Benchmarking of
406 lignin-derived carbon materials based on CO₂ uptake values are given in **Table S2**. Across the
407 literature, the highest CO₂ uptake reported for lignin-derived carbon is 13.6 mmol/g (298 K,
408 1–10 atm), which is achieved by KOH activation along with N-doping using urea, which
409 resulted in a BET surface area of 3000 m²/g. Moreover, previously reported lignin-based
410 carbon materials with activation demonstrated lower CO₂ uptake values compared to those
411 achieved in the present work.^{73,74} However, lignin-based carbon materials without heteroatom
412 doping or activation have always demonstrated lower CO₂ uptake values.^{70,75} In the only study
413 explicitly reporting CO₂ sorption by carbonized lignin-based electrospun fibers, a CO₂ uptake
414 of 1.56 mmol/g was reported; however, the fibers relied on a fossil-derived binder polymer,
415 poly(acrylonitrile), rather than a biobased alternative.⁷⁶

416 The shape of the CO₂ adsorption isotherm provides mechanistic insight into the nature
417 of gas–solid interactions and the chemical transformations occurring during
418 thermostabilization and subsequent carbonization. The CO₂ adsorption isotherm shown in **Fig.**
419 **7e** indicates strong adsorbate–adsorbent interactions, evidenced by a steep initial CO₂ uptake
420 at low relative pressures and a clear deviation from a purely physisorptive adsorption profile,

421 suggesting the contribution of chemisorptive interactions.⁷⁷ As native SKL contains negligible
422 nitrogen, the observed effect may arise from nitrogen incorporation during thermostabilization
423 as DMF begins to decompose at elevated temperatures. Although DMF evaporates at ~150 °C
424 and thermally degrades at ~300 °C, partial retention of nitrogen in the material cannot be
425 entirely ruled out. This has been seen by the TGA analysis of thermostabilized fibers as shown
426 in the **Fig. S1**. The gradual decrease in weight percentage from 300 °C is also attributed to the
427 hydrolysis of DMF to amine functionalities⁷⁸ along with the degradation of lignin's backbone.
428 At temperatures above 300°C, the primary decomposition of lignin occurs by homolytic
429 cleavage of the C—C and C—O bonds, resulting in the formation of low-molecular weight
430 phenolic compounds such as guaiacol, methyl guaiacol and ethyl guaiacol.⁷⁹ Around 400 °C,
431 homolysis of β -O-4 bonds produces phenoxy radicals.⁸⁰ The flattening of the thermogram in
432 **Fig. S1** after 600 °C can be attributed to aromatic condensation.⁷⁹ The resulting amine
433 functionalities from DMF decomposition after 300 °C, even at lower percentages may act as
434 basic sites capable of enhancing CO₂ affinity for the carbonized fibers which has ~0.5–5 atomic
435 % of nitrogen as per the elemental analysis by EDS (**Table 1**, **Fig S8**, **Fig. S9**, **Fig. S10** and
436 **Fig. S11**), contributing to the observed CO₂ sorption behavior.

437 The samples with higher lignin content (70 and 80 wt.% with lower BET surface area)
438 were found to have higher nitrogen content from the elemental analysis. Nitrogen
439 functionalities significantly enhance the CO₂ uptake. As a result, even with lower surface area
440 and microporosity, the enhanced interaction between CO₂ molecules and the N-containing
441 functionalities compensate for the reduced number of adsorption sites, which eventually leads
442 to comparable overall CO₂ uptake observed for the samples. It has been reported that lignin-
443 based nanofibers stabilized at 350 °C exhibit a nitrogen content of 0.48%, whereas samples
444 stabilized below 300 °C show no detectable nitrogen. This was attributed either to the presence
445 of residual DMF or to the protein residues inherently present in lignin.⁵⁹ Similarly, solid-state

446 ^{13}C MAS spectrum of carbonized SKL–CA nanofibers with 80 wt.% of SKL is shown in **Fig.**
447 **S13**, which has high spectral noise due to the highly conductive nature of the sample, and the
448 peak at 125 ppm is typical for aromatic carbon atoms.⁸¹ Due to the low signal-to-noise ratio,
449 trace levels of nitrogen functionalities cannot be excluded solely based on solid-state ^{13}C MAS
450 spectrum, as EDS analysis revealed traces of nitrogen in the samples. Similar observations
451 were made when Zirconium–ellagate metal–organic framework was made using DMF as co-
452 solvent, where DMF hydrolysed to dimethylammonium cations, which was found in the pores
453 of the MOFs after activation.⁷⁸

454 To investigate the potential for sequential material utilization, methylene blue-loaded
455 electrospun nanofibers were subjected to thermostabilization and carbonization to evaluate
456 their potential repurposing as CO_2 sorbents. Methylene blue adsorbed electrospun nanofibers
457 with SKL content 80 wt.% were also subjected to thermostabilization followed by
458 carbonization as per the protocol mentioned in **Fig. 5** to evaluate if the spent fibers can be
459 repurposed as CO_2 sorbents. The resulting carbonized fibers exhibited comparable CO_2
460 sorption capacity (2.2 mmol/g) as that of carbonized fibers without dye uptake (3.1 mmol/g)
461 which is shown in **Fig. 7f**. A slightly lower value of CO_2 sorption capacity is observed for the
462 carbonized spent fibers, due to the partial coverage or blockage of surface sites by residual
463 species originating from the adsorbed dye during carbonization, which is further clarified from
464 the SEM image of the carbonized spent fibers shown in **Fig. S2**. From the SEM image of the
465 carbonized spent fibers, it is observed that the surface is covered with residues originating from
466 the methylene blue dye, and from the EDS mapping it is observed that the surface has presence
467 of elements such as N, S, Cl, O, and C, where N, S, and Cl are originating solely from the dye
468 residues. The digital images of spent fibers before and after carbonization and the SEM image
469 of spent fibers after thermostabilization are also shown in **Fig. S2**.

470

471

472 **Conclusions**

473 This study demonstrates the incorporation of up to 80% of softwood kraft lignin in electrospun
474 nanofibers without any chemical modification or solvent fractionation of the lignin.
475 Electrospun nanofiber mats produced from mixtures of cellulose acetate and softwood kraft
476 lignin exhibited effective dye adsorption from aqueous solutions, with cationic methylene blue
477 used as the model pollutant. The nanofibers with different compositions were subjected to
478 carbonization at 1000 °C in an inert atmosphere after thermally stabilizing them at 300 °C in
479 air. The variation in lignin content influenced both carbon yield and surface area, with higher
480 lignin content yielding more carbon yield but lower surface area due to reduced cellulose
481 acetate content and restricted pore development. The CO₂ adsorption behavior reflected a trade-
482 off between these parameters rather than monotonic dependence on surface area. As an attempt
483 to demonstrate multipurpose sequential use of the electrospun fiber mats, they were first used
484 for methylene blue adsorption and subsequently carbonized for CO₂ sorption with promising
485 results. Future work will focus on understanding how CO₂ sorption depends on the chemical
486 structure of carbon materials derived from lignin-based precursor nanofibers.

487

488 **Experimental section**

489 **Materials**

490 The Softwood kraft lignin (SKL) was obtained from UPM (BioPiva™100, Finland), Cellulose
491 acetate (CA, degree of deacetylation 37%), acetone, and N,N'-dimethylformamide (DMF) were
492 purchased from Honeywell. Methylene blue was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. All the
493 chemicals were used as received.

494 **Methods**

495 **Electrospinning**

496 SKL and CA were dissolved in a 1:2.4 v/v DMF/Acetone mixture, at 20 wt. % total
497 concentrations, in different wt.% ratios; 0:100, 50:50, 60:40, 70:30, and 80:20 of SKL and CA
498 respectively. All solutions were prepared by magnetic stirring at 1000 rpm at room temperature
499 for 24–36 h. Sonication was done if it was hard to dissolve the solids.

500 A volume of 20 mL was placed in a syringe fitted with a Hamilton Point style 2 needle having
501 Gauge size 21 and length 51mm, which was attached to the holder in a horizontal configuration
502 and coupled to a high-voltage power supply providing 20 kV. The needle tip was placed 15 cm
503 from an aluminium foil wrapped around a rotating drum collector, and a positively charged jet
504 from the syringe tip was projected onto the negatively charged collector. Nanofibers were then
505 carefully removed from the collector plate. All experiments were performed at room
506 temperature. The polymer solution was dispensed at 0.04 mL/min. The electrospinning
507 operation was carried for 5–8 h to have enough material after carbonization.

508 **Dye adsorption**

509 Initially, dye adsorption experiments were carried out using methylene blue dye solutions with
510 initial concentrations ranging from 7–142 mg/L. The dye solutions were made in deionised
511 water. 30 mg of SKL–CA electrospun nanofibers with 80:20 composition (in wt.%) were
512 placed in 10 mL of methylene blue dye solutions with different concentrations. Equilibrium
513 concentrations of the dye solutions after dye adsorption were measured after 24 h agitation at
514 room temperature at a rate of 100 rpm (Incu-Shaker™, Fisherbrand). After adsorption, the
515 fibers were separated via centrifugation (10000 rpm for 10 min using Universal 320 centrifuge)
516 and the supernatant was used for UV-Vis absorbance measurements. Similarly, kinetics of dye
517 adsorption was determined by performing experiments in the above-mentioned method by

518 keeping the samples at different time intervals ranging from 0–24 h. The spent fibers were
519 dried and used for thermostabilization followed by carbonization.

520 The equilibrium adsorption capacity ($Q_{e,adsorption}$) was measured using the following equation:⁴⁷

$$521 \quad Q_{e,adsorption} = (C_0 - C_e) \times \frac{V}{m} \quad (1)$$

522 Dye removal efficiency was calculated using the following equation:

$$523 \quad \% \text{ Dye Removal} = \frac{[C_0 - C_e]}{C_0} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

524 C_0 is the concentration of the initial dye solution, C_e is the equilibrium concentration of the
525 dye, V is the volume of the dye solution L, and m is the mass of the adsorbent in g.

526 The experimental equilibrium data were fitted by applying Langmuir, Freundlich and
527 Langmuir–Freundlich models as per the equations 3, 4 and 5 respectively.⁵⁴

$$528 \quad Q_e = \frac{Q_{max} \times K_L \times C_e}{1 + K_L \times C_e} \quad (3)$$

$$529 \quad Q_e = K_F \times C_e^{1/n_F} \quad (4)$$

$$530 \quad Q_e = \frac{Q_{max} \times (K_{LF} \times C_e)^{n_{LF}}}{1 + (K_{LF} \times C_e)^{n_{LF}}} \quad (5)$$

531

532 **Thermostabilization**

533 The stabilization of SKL–CA electrospun nanofibers with different composition (in wt.%) was
534 performed using a muffle furnace (Nabertherm) with a heating rate of 2 °C/min with a final
535 temperature of 300 °C in air and then holding the sample isothermally for 1 h.

536 Yield after thermostabilization (Y_{TS} , %) with respect to the initial weight of electrospun
537 nanofibers was calculated using the following equation:

$$538 \quad \text{Thermostabilization Yield } (Y_{TS}, \%) = \frac{W_1}{W_0} \times 100 \quad (6)$$

539 Where, W_0 is the initial weight of electrospun nanofibers and W_1 is the weight after
540 thermostabilization.

541 **Carbonization**

542 Carbonization of stabilized electrospun SKL–CA nanofibers with different composition (in
543 wt.%) was carried out in a tube furnace (Carbolite) under Argon gas flow, by heating from 25–
544 1000 °C at 5 °C/min, followed by a hold at 1000 °C for 1 h.

545 Yield after carbonization (Y_C , %) with respect to the initial weight of electrospun nanofibers
546 was calculated using the following equation:

$$547 \quad \text{Carbonization Yield } (Y_C, \%) = \frac{W_2}{W_0} \times 100 \quad (7)$$

548 Where, W_2 is the weight after carbonization.

549 Similarly, yield after carbonization ($Y_{C/TS}$, %) with respect to the weight of thermostabilized
550 electrospun nanofibers was calculated using the following equation:

$$551 \quad \text{Carbonization Yield } (Y_{C/TS}, \%) = \frac{W_2}{W_1} \times 100 \quad (8)$$

552 **Characterization**

553 **ATR-FTIR spectroscopy**

554 Attenuated Total Reflectance-Fourier Transform Infrared (ATR-FTIR) spectroscopy was used
555 for the analysis of functional groups in the SKL, CA and electrospun and carbonized nanofiber
556 samples with different composition (in wt.%) of SKL–CA, by using a Varian 610-IR
557 Spectrometer equipped with a diamond ATR Optics. The spectra were measured from 400–
558 4000 cm^{-1} with a total of 32 scans.

559 **UV-Vis Spectrophotometry**

560 Absorbance measurements of methylene blue dye solutions before and after adsorption using
561 SKL–CA electrospun nanofiber 80–20 composition (in wt.%) were performed using a UV-Vis
562 spectrophotometer (Genesys 150 UV-Vis spectrophotometer, Thermo Scientific) with cuvettes
563 (path length $l = 1$ cm) at time 0 and after 24 h for obtaining the adsorption isotherm and at
564 regular intervals for studying the adsorption kinetics, which was conducted at a wavelength λ
565 $= 664$ nm.

566 **Water contact angle**

567 Small piece of SKL–CA nanofibers with 80–20 composition (in wt.%) was fixed to a
568 microscope slide for contact angle measurements. 2 μ L of water was added to the surface using
569 Drop Shape Analyzer DSA25E (KRÜSS instruments, Germany). Measurements were recorded
570 over time and analyzed using ADVANCE software (KRÜSS instruments, Germany).

571 **Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA)**

572 Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) was used to study the thermal degradation behavior of
573 SKL, CA, and electrospun nanofiber samples with different compositions (in wt.%) of SKL–
574 CA using Perkin Elmer TGA4 model with an aluminum oxide pan, using 5–20 mg of samples.
575 The temperature ramp was from RT–300 °C with a heating rate of 2 °C per min in air and an
576 isothermal hold at 300 °C for 60 minutes. For thermostabilized samples, carbonization was also
577 performed in the same instrument by heating the sample up to 1000 °C in an N₂ atmosphere
578 with a heating rate of 5 °C per min and an isothermal hold for 60 minutes at 1000 °C.

579 **Raman spectroscopy**

580 The graphitic structure of carbonized electrospun nanofiber samples with different
581 compositions (in wt.%) of SKL–CA was investigated using Raman spectroscopy, recorded on

582 a Horiba Labram S3000 instrument via a 10x magnification lens using a 532 nm laser, with an
583 acquisition time of 3 s and 25 accumulations in the range of 200–3999 cm^{-1} .

584 **Imaging and EDS analysis**

585 A JSM-IT 800 scanning electron microscope was used to image SKL–CA electrospun
586 nanofibers with different compositions (in wt.%) and thermostabilized and carbonized samples.
587 Electrospun samples and thermostabilized samples were coated for 60 s with gold using a JFC-
588 1200 fine coater before the SEM imaging. The gold particles added by sputtering are about 5–
589 15 nm in size. Same instrument was used for elemental analysis of the carbonized samples in
590 HV vacuum mode with an accelerating voltage of 15 kV, probe current ranging from 0.16–
591 0.17 nA, and the working distance was maintained from 10–11 mm. The dead-time was set for
592 3%. Digital photographs of the Electrospinning solutions, SKL–CA electrospun nanofibers
593 with different compositions (in wt.%) and thermostabilized and carbonized samples were
594 acquired using an iPhone 13 Pro digital camera.

595 **X-Ray diffraction (XRD)**

596 X-Ray diffraction (XRD) patterns of the SKL, CA, electrospun nanofiber samples with
597 different compositions (in wt.%) of SKL–CA samples and the thermostabilized and carbonized
598 nanofiber samples were obtained using a Bruker D8 Discover Diffractometer in reflection
599 mode using Cu $K\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda = 1.5418 \text{ \AA}$), 2θ ranging from 5° – 85° with an increment of 0.01
600 and a rotation speed of 15 rotations per min.

601 **CO₂ uptake and BET surface area**

602 Micromeritics® Gemini™ VII Series (model 2390a) was used to measure the BET (Brunauer,
603 Emmett, and Teller) surface area and CO₂ adsorption capacity of the carbonized electrospun
604 SKL–CA fibers. All samples were degassed at 150 °C for 12 h. BET surface area measurement
605 was performed using 90–190 mg of samples with N₂ at 77.34 K using 20 points with relative

606 pressure (p/p°) ranging from 0.005–0.98. Free space was evaluated using He gas, which is not
607 adsorbed by the samples. The same samples were used for studying CO₂ adsorption capacity
608 after degassing at 150 °C for 12 h. The temperature was kept constant at 0°C using an ice bath,
609 and 18 points were measured with absolute pressure (kPa) ranging from 0.12–101 kPa.

610 **Solid-state nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy (ss-NMR)**

611 Solid-state ¹³C MAS spectrum of carbonized SKL–CA nanofibers with 80–20 composition (in
612 wt.%) was collected at a magnetic field of 9.4 T with a Bruker Avance-III spectrometer using
613 a 4 mm probe head and a 12 kHz MAS rate. Acquisition involved a 90-degree excitation pulse
614 of 3.2 μs (~78 kHz rf nutation power) and 16384 signal transients were collected with a
615 relaxation delay of 5 s. No proton decoupling or cross-polarization magic-angle-spinning
616 (CPMAS) could be employed due to the highly conductive character of the sample, which
617 hindered tuning/matching of the proton channel. ¹³C chemical shift is reported with respect to
618 tetramethylsilane (TMS).

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627 **Conflict of interest**

628 The authors have no conflicts to declare.

629 **Author contributions**

630 U.T.V. Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Validation, Formal analysis,

631 Visualization, Writing – Original draft, Writing – Review and editing.

632 F.W. Investigation, Writing – Review and editing.

633 M.E. Investigation, Validation, Writing – Review and editing.

634 A.J. Investigation, Writing – Review and editing.

635 M.H.S. Funding acquisition, Project administration, Supervision, Writing – Review and

636 editing.

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